

Kinetics and Mechanism of Reactions of the Quasi-aromatic Complex $[\text{Ni}(\text{PnAO})\cdot 6\text{H}]^{\circ}$ with Aromatic Aldehydes

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Kinetics and mechanism of the reactions of aromatic aldehydes with a quasi-aromatic nickel(II) complex $[\text{Ni}(\text{PnAO})\cdot 6\text{H}]^{\circ}$ have been studied in acidic media (pH=1-2; EtOH : H₂O, 1 : 2) and a competitive consecutive second order reaction mechanism is proposed. Effects of acidity, solvent and temperature on the reaction rate constants have been studied and the results support the proposed mechanism. A linear free energy relationship between the rate constants of the different *para*-substituent aromatic aldehydes and the Hammett parameters of the substituents was obtained.

The quasi-aromatic complex (2,2,3,9,10,10-hexamethyl-5,7-dioxa-6-hydra-1,4,8,11-tetraazacyclotetradeca-3,8,11,13-tetraene)nickel(II) $[\text{Ni}(\text{PnAO})\cdot 6\text{H}]^{\circ}$ (AH) has many interesting properties, especially in the *para*-position of the metal ion¹. Previously we reported the kinetics and mechanism of reaction of the complex with formaldehyde and a complicated mechanism was proposed. We report herein the kinetics and the mechanism of the reactions of $[\text{Ni}(\text{PnAO})\cdot 6\text{H}]^{\circ}$ with aromatic aldehydes. The purpose of this study is to investigate the effect of the *para*-substituents of the aromatic aldehydes on the rate constants.

$[\text{Ni}(\text{PnAO})\cdot 6\text{H}]^{\circ}$

Results and Discussion

Mechanism of reaction : In weak acidic solutions, the visible spectra (Fig. 1) of the reaction of AH with aromatic aldehydes were very similar to that of the reaction of AH with formaldehydes, when aldehydes are not in large excess. However, in large excess of aromatic aldehydes, the peak of absorbance of the intermediate did not go down, which means that the third step taking place for the reaction of formaldehyde with AH did not occur. In strong acidic solution, although the spectra of the reaction were not similar to that in weak acidic solution, the change of the spectra with

Fig. 1. Change of the spectra of the reaction of $[\text{Ni}(\text{PnAO})\cdot 6\text{H}]^{\circ}$ with benzaldehyde with time under weak acidity condition. The absorbance at 510 nm shows the decomposition reactions. The last curve was recorded 3 days after the reaction started.

time was very simple. After the reaction was complete, and neutralising the solution with NaOH, the spectra of the reaction system changed into the spectra of the reaction product in weak acidic

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The scheme may be simply written as:

where $\text{R}=\text{H}, \text{CH}_3, \text{OH}, \text{OCH}_3, \text{Cl}, \text{NO}_2$.

Scheme 1

solution. That means that the reaction mechanism is the same as in weak acidic solution.

On the other hand, crystals of the final products were obtained when the reactions proceeded in pure water solution and the spectra of the final products were very similar to that of ACH_2A which was the second-step product of the reaction of formaldehyde with AH. Furthermore, the ir spectra of the crystals were also very similar to that of ACH_2A and the crystal analysis of the product of the reaction of benzaldehyde with AH identified the structure as $\text{Ph}-\text{CH}-\text{A}_2$. All these facts showed that the final products of the reactions of aromatic aldehydes with AH had structures as $p\text{-R.C}_6\text{H}_4.\text{CHA}_2$.

According to above results and comparing with the mechanism of the reaction of formaldehyde with AH, we propose the mechanism of the reaction of aromatic aldehydes with AH as shown in Scheme 1.

Method of evaluating rate constants: Because the second step is much faster than the first one, so when the aldehydes are in large excess, k_1 but not k_2 can be evaluated by pseudo-first order program. Another problem is that the intermediate $p\text{-R.C}_6\text{H}_4.\text{CH}(\text{OH})\text{-A}$ can not be obtained, so the method employed in determining the rate constant of the second step of the reaction of formaldehyde with AH does not work here.

The mechanism of the system studied is a typical competitive consecutive second order reaction. For this kind of reaction, there are many discussions on

the methods for evaluation of the rate constants from the experiment data³, but all of them are complicated and inaccurate. We used a fitting method to treat the experiment data. The reactions may be expressed as

where Ald stands for aldehydes, B for the intermediate $p\text{-R.C}_6\text{H}_4.\text{CH}(\text{OH})\text{-A}$ and C for the product $p\text{-R.C}_6\text{H}_4.\text{CH}\text{-A}_2$. The rate equations may be written as

$$d[\text{AH}]/dt = -k_1[\text{Ald}]_0[\text{AH}] - k_2[\text{AH}][\text{B}] \quad (1)$$

$$d[\text{C}]/dt = k_2[\text{AH}][\text{B}] \quad (2)$$

For materials balance,

$$[\text{B}] = [\text{AH}]_0 - [\text{AH}] - 2[\text{C}] \quad (3)$$

one obtains,

$$d[\text{AH}]/dt = -k_1[\text{Ald}]_0[\text{AH}] - k_2[\text{AH}]([\text{AH}]_0 - [\text{AH}] - 2[\text{C}]) \quad (4)$$

$$d[\text{C}]/dt = k_2[\text{AH}]([\text{AH}]_0 - [\text{AH}] - 2[\text{C}]) \quad (5)$$

Let $[\text{AH}]_r = [\text{AH}]/[\text{AH}]_0$, $[\text{C}]_r = 2[\text{C}]/[\text{AH}]_0$, $k_1' = k_1[\text{Ald}]_0$, $k_2' = k_2[\text{AH}]_0$, since $[\text{Ald}]_0 \gg [\text{AH}]_0$ in the experiment (at least 70 times) so $[\text{Ald}] \approx [\text{Ald}]_0$. From equations (4) and (5), we have

$$d[\text{AH}]_r/dt = -k_1'[\text{AH}]_r - k_2'[\text{AH}]_r(1 - [\text{AH}]_r - [\text{C}]_r) \quad (6)$$

$$d[\text{C}]_r/dt = k_2'[\text{AH}]_r(1 - [\text{AH}]_r - [\text{C}]_r) \quad (7)$$

From the absorbance at a suitable wavelength, $[C]_r$ may be determined,

$$[C]_r = \Delta A / \Delta A_\infty = (A_t - A_0) / (A_\infty - A_0) \quad (8)$$

By means of equations (6), (7) and (8), the rate constants k'_1 and k'_2 can be determined as follows: (i) Some assumed values of k'_1 and k'_2 are substituted into the equations (6) and (7), then Runge Kutta program⁴ is used to solve the equations and obtain a series of $[C]_r$ at different times. (ii) Comparing the series of $[C]_r$ with the experiment data $\Delta A / \Delta A_\infty$, the standard deviation S is calculated. (iii) Using Gaus-Newton-Marquardt non-linear regression program⁵, k'_1 and k'_2 are determined at minimum S . These k'_1 and k'_2 values are the observed rate constants.

The experimental data and the nature of plot shown in Fig. 2, show that the method is successful. Furthermore, we also used steady state method and pseudo-first order program to evaluate the rate constants of the first step (k'_1) which were in agreement with the corresponding values obtained by the curve fitting method (Table 1).

Fig. 2. Fitting result of experiment data with evaluated curve.

Rate constants of reactions: k'_1 and k'_2 values at different initial aldehyde concentrations are listed

TABLE 1—RATE CONSTANTS REACTIONS OF $[\text{Ni}(\text{PnAO})_6\text{H}]^{\circ}$ WITH DIFFERENT *para*-SUBSTITUTED ($\text{R}=\text{OH}, \text{OCH}_3, \text{CH}_3, \text{H}, \text{Cl}, \text{NO}_2$) AROMATIC ALDEHYDES^a
Temp = 30°, pH = 1.77, EtOH : H₂O = 1 : 2, $[\text{AH}]_0 = 6.17 \times 10^{-3}$ (when R = OH, CH₃, OCH₃), 9.27×10^{-3} (when R = H, Cl), 1.55×10^{-2} (when R = NO₂)

R	$[\text{Ald}]_0 \times 10^3$	$k'_1{}^a \text{ s}^{-1}$	$k'_1{}^b \text{ s}^{-1}$	$k_1{}^c \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$	$k_2{}^d \text{ s}^{-1}$	$k_2{}^d \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$
OH	2.81	0.001 87	0.001 95	0.687	3.40	903
	2.34	0.001 58	0.001 63			
	1.87	0.001 29	0.001 30			
	1.41	0.000 98	0.000 98			
OCH ₃	6.05	0.003 72	0.003 73	0.616	3.62	979
	5.35	0.003 28	0.003 30			
	4.62	0.002 83	0.002 85			
	3.83	0.002 37	0.002 37			
CH ₃	7.32	0.003 40	0.003 43	0.468	3.36	904
	6.20	0.002 87	0.002 92			
	5.10	0.002 35	0.002 38			
	4.00	0.001 88	0.001 88			
H	9.55	0.002 52	0.002 52	0.263	2.92	524
	8.00	0.002 10	0.002 12			
	6.50	0.001 68	0.001 70			
	4.80	0.001 27	0.001 28			
Cl	7.87	0.001 34	0.001 34	0.170	3.40	609
	7.21	0.001 20	0.001 23			
	6.50	0.001 09	0.001 06			
	5.80	0.000 97	0.000 99			
NO ₂	21.18	0.005 38	0.005 42	0.246	2.93	315
	19.4	0.004 75	0.004 80			
	17.0	0.004 18	0.004 18			
	14.6	0.003 58	0.003 55			

*All units of concentration are in mol dm⁻³. ^aEvaluated by pseudo-first order program. ^bEvaluated by the fitting program. ^cObtained from slope of the straight line of plotting k'_1 s (column 4) against the concentrations of aldehydes (column 2). ^dObtained from the average of k'_2 s (column 5).

in Table 1. That k'_2 is about 100 times larger than k'_1 is consistent with our proposed mechanism. It is also seen from Table 1 that for the same substituent with different initial aldehyde concentrations, a straight line was obtained between k'_1 s and initial aldehyde concentrations with correlation coefficients 0.9999, but k'_2 s remained unchanged. All these facts support our proposed mechanism.

Effect of acidity of solution: Because of the presence of decomposition reactions, we had to study the effect of acidity of the solution on the rate of reaction in a rather narrow range of acidity (0.01–0.05 mol dm⁻³ HCl). However, the experimental results showed that the rate constants changed appreciably (Table 2).

For any substituent, there is a good linear relationship between the first step rate constants and the concentration of the hydrogen ion (Fig. 3). The slopes (k_H) of the straight lines are listed in the last column of Table 2.

TABLE 2—RATE CONSTANTS AT DIFFERENT ACIDITY*

 Temp. = 30°, EtOH : H₂O = 1 : 2, [AH]₀ = 6.17 × 10⁻⁵ – 1.55 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³

R	k dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	[H ⁺] (mol dm ⁻³)						k _H
		0.0327	0.0203	0.0169	0.0135	0.0118	0.0101	
OH	k ₁	0.943	0.824	0.694	0.558		0.427	19.5
OCH ₃	k ₁		0.721	0.616	0.514		0.391	16.4
CH ₃	k ₁		0.561	0.468	0.367		0.278	14.2
H	k ₁		0.325	0.263	0.200		0.139	9.32
Cl	k ₁			0.164	0.133	0.117	0.102	4.67
NO ₂	k ₁		0.282	0.245	0.203		0.161	6.07
OH	k ₂	1635	1290	903	698		509	

*All data except the last line were evaluated by the pseudo-first order program.

 Fig. 3. Linear relationship between rate constant and hydrogen ion concentration; R = (1) OH, (2) OCH₃, (3) CH₃, (4) H, (5) Cl and (6) NO₂.

The effect of acidity may be ascribed to the protonation of the carbonyl group on the aldehydes.

 After protonation, the aldehydes are much more reactive towards [Ni(PnAO)-6H]⁰. In the first step, both aldehyde and protonated aldehyde can react with [Ni(PnAO)-6H]⁰, and so the observed rate constant is the sum of two reactions.

$$k_1' = k_A[\text{Ald}] + k_P[\text{HAld}^+] = (k_A + k_P K_H [\text{H}^+])[\text{Ald}]_0 \quad (\text{i})$$

 where [Ald] and [HAld⁺] denote the concentrations of aldehyde and protonated aldehyde, respectively, and [Ald]₀ stands for the initial concentration of aldehyde.

That is :

$$k_1 = k_A + k_P K_H [\text{H}^+] \quad (\text{ii})$$

 Equation (ii) shows that there is a linear relationship between k_1 and [H⁺] and the slope of the line is $k_H = k_P K_H$. This is consistent with our experimental result.

 The effect of the acidity of the solution on the second step is also appreciable, but no linear relationship exists between the rate constants and [H⁺].

 Effect of para-substituents of the aldehydes on rate constants : From Tables 1 and 2 it is clear that k_1 and k_H increase with the electron-repelling ability of the substituents, but for k_2 there is no regularity. Electron repelling substituents render the carbonyl group in the aldehydes more basic, so they react easily with proton, i.e. the protonation equilibrium constants (K_H) increase. As discussed above, k_H are larger than k_A , and so k_1 and k_H increase with the electron repelling ability of the substituents although k_A would theoretically decrease with the

electron-repelling ability of the substituents. If only the effect of the substituents on K_H is considered, a linear free energy relationship will exist between k_H and Hammett σ parameters of the substituents. The result is shown in Fig. 4. Except for NO_2 , the other five points lie on a straight line having correlation coefficient 0.991.

Fig. 4. Linear free energy relationship between the acid catalytic rate constant and Hammett parameter.

Effect of solvent: k_1 and k_2 values increase with increasing water : alcohol ratio.

We have determined the pH of the solution with identical acidity but having different water and alcohol ratio. For example, when the solution had an observed acidity of $0.0169 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ but containing no alcohol or 1/3 alcohol, the pH of the solution was 1.770 and 1.773, respectively. This shows that the effect of solvent was not due to the activity of the hydrogen ion.

TABLE 3—RATE CONSTANTS IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS

R=OH, Temp. = 30° , pH=1.77, $[\text{AH}]_0 = 6.17 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

k $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$	H_2O (%)				
	50	60	66.7	73	75
k_1	0.161	0.345	0.687	1.26	2.60
k_2	434	668	903	1131	1611

It is probable that the most important step in acid-catalytic process is proton transfer from the solvent to the carbonyl group of the aldehyde. There is evidence⁶ that the transfer of proton in solution proceeds by hydrogen bonding between substrate and solvent.

Water can form a much stronger hydrogen bond than alcohol, therefore it has stronger ability to catalyse the reaction.

Effect of temperature: The effect of temperature on k_1 is presented in Table 4. From the plots of

TABLE 4—RATE CONSTANTS OF THE FIRST STEP AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES*

R	k_1 ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$)				$\Delta H^\ddagger$ kJ mol^{-1}	$\Delta S^\ddagger$ $\text{JK}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$
	30°	35°	40°	45°		
OH	0.694	0.783	0.907	1.026	20.8 ± 0.8	-180 ± 2
OCH_3	0.611	0.710	0.794	0.895	17.3 ± 0.8	-192 ± 3
CH_3	0.470	0.567	0.657	0.743	21.9 ± 1.4	-179 ± 5
H	0.263	0.311	0.386	0.466	28.5 ± 1.2	-162 ± 4
Cl	0.170	0.254	0.363	0.470	52.4 ± 3	-87 ± 9
NO_2	0.246	0.282	0.322	0.365	18.6 ± 0.09	-176 ± 0.3

*All data were evaluated by pseudo-first order program. Errors given for $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger$ are standard deviations.

In (k_1/T) against $1/T$, we obtained the observed activation parameters $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger$ (Table 4).

The rate constant k_H includes the protonation equilibrium constant K_H and while K_H decreases with the electron-repelling ability of the substituents, the activation enthalpy in turn decreases with the electron repelling ability of the substituents.

Experimental

$[\text{Ni}(\text{PnAO})\cdot 6\text{H}]^\circ$ was prepared by the reported method⁸. The aromatic aldehydes (A.R.) were purified by distillation under reduced pressure in N_2 environment when the sample was liquid or by recrystallisation when the sample was solid. The samples was preserved under non-oxygen environment. Ethanol and HCl (G.R.) were used.

The visible spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu UV-240 spectrophotometer equipped with thermostated ($\pm 0.5^\circ$) cell housing and ir spectra on an OYE UNICAN SP3-300 spectrophotometer. Kinetic parameters were evaluated on an Apple II micro-computer.

Selection of experimental conditions: The reactions of $[\text{Ni}(\text{PnAO})\cdot 6\text{H}]^\circ$ with aromatic aldehydes were acid-catalysed and were very slow in neutral solution. But the complex $[\text{Ni}(\text{PnAO})\cdot 6\text{H}]^\circ$ decom-

posed in acid to complicated products as indicated by the decay of the absorbance peak at 510 nm (Fig. 1).

Experiments showed that in the pH range 1–2, the reaction of the complex with the aldehydes went to completion within 10–40 min while the background decomposition reaction was observed only after 1–2 h. The reactions were therefore studied in the pH range 1–2.

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